

Planning and Designing of a Skyscraper using ETABS and BIM Tool Software

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ABSTRACT

Today, skyscrapers and other large buildings are common in India's main cities. This study applies a BIM method to skyscraper construction technology. AutoCAD is used for skyscraper planning, and Revit is used for modelling. A comparison is made between advanced structural analysis tools like ETABS and BIM (AutoCAD, Revit). In the proposed study, ETABS created and evaluated a skyscraper model in accordance with IS-875-Part1-3 and IS1893-2016-Part1. Today, skyscrapers and other large buildings are common in India's main cities. This study applies a BIM method to skyscraper construction technology. AutoCAD is used for skyscraper planning, and Revit is used for modelling. A comparison is made between advanced structural analysis tools like ETABS and BIM (AutoCAD, Revit). In the proposed study, ETABS created and evaluated a skyscraper model in accordance with IS-875-Part1-3 and IS1893-2016-Part1. The behavior of 40 storey building which lies in seismic zone II has been studied. The Dynamic effects is find by Response spectrum method. One of the parameters such as base shear obtained by Equivalent static method and Response spectrum method has compared. All the parameters like Story displacement, Story drift, Base shear, Overturning moments, Acceleration & Time period are calculated After results we concluded that BIM makes the entire building process simpler and more efficient. The conclusion is documented in the literature i.e., the stórey overturning moment is inversely proportional with storey height. And Base shear for Equivalent Static Method (ESM) compared with Response Spectrum Method (RSM), to ensured that minimum strength of designed structure using RSM is similar to strength of designed structure using ESM, so scaling have to done. All other parameters are to be found to under maximum permissible limit.

Keywords–Skyscrapers, BIM, AutoCAD, Revit, ETABS, Dynamic Effects, Response Spectrum Method (RSM), Equivalent Static Method (ESM).

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Skyscrapers

A skyscraper is a large, continuously occupied structure of 40 stories or more that is primarily intended for offices, commercial, and residential applications. Although it can also be referred to as a high-rise, structures taller than 50 m are most commonly referred to as skyscrapers (164 ft). Supertall buildings are those that are taller than 300 m (984 ft), while Megatall buildings are those that are taller than 600 m (1,969 ft).

Designing and building skyscrapers requires creating living, secure spaces in incredibly tall buildings. It is necessary for the buildings to support their own weight, endure wind and earthquakes, and protect residents from fire. They must provide the residents with amenities and a pleasant atmosphere, but they must also be conveniently accessible, especially on upper levels.

Skyscraper design difficulties are among the most difficult because of the fine balances that must be struck between engineering, economics, and construction management.

1.2 BIM (Building Information Modelling)

BIM is an intelligent model-based method for creating and managing information throughout the course of a construction project's complete life cycle. BIM integrates information from several fields to create detailed digital representations that may be managed on an open cloud platform for real-time collaboration. When used in AEC projects, BIM improves visibility, decision-making, offers more sustainable solutions, and reduces costs.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1) N.O. NAWARI (2014) Focuses on the lessons that may be learned from using Building Information Modeling (BIM) in the instruction of structural design. When teaching structural analysis and design, BIM was used as a framework. BIM tools were then applied as the major method for extending various types of structural engineering knowledge that focus on digital activities. Several analytical models are utilised to carry out various structural analysis and design education tasks. Structural analytical models are built utilising BIM technologies. A number of tools and simulation techniques are used to build a BIM model for carrying out structural engineering design, including beams, frames, trusses, slabs, foundations, and finite element analysis.

The suggested BIM approach aims to: (1) promote in-depth understanding of the fundamentals of structural analysis and design; (2) promote collaborative thinking as a core activity; (3) enhance digital modelling; and (4) promote professional qualities to meet the demands of today's as well as tomorrow's integrated practise environment.

2) REN-JWO TSAY (2019) For many structural analysis programmes, a streamlined element analysis model was created using the finite element approach. However, there is a little gap in the actual behavioural impacts due to the model's simplification, and this causes the analysis results to deviate from actual conditions like the layout of RC section reinforcing steel. So an important engineering difficulty is how to accurately characterise the genuine condition for RC detail section. The real section and reinforcement impact of the 3D member model will be established using building information modelling (BIM) software in conjunction with an APP programme. In this study, we used Autodesk Revit, a BIM tool, to create a structural model with geometry and reinforcement for the RC system. We then converted the model into the ETABS analysis tool to acquire regional structure behaviour and investigate genuine structural security.

By combining BIM Revit and ETABS analysis, we can find findings for structural detail analysis that will improve the precision of structural analysis. In order to overcome the gaps from traditional simplified numerical models, the designer can obtain the genuine behaviour using Revit reinforced detail layout.

3) VISHAL UTTAM MISAL, HARSH BHAVESH DIWANI, TANISHQ RAVINDRA RANE, SAISH SHAMKANT KADAM, ASHISH SHASHIKUMAR (2022) Due to its vast applicability in designing, analysis, planning, and other processes, Building Information Modelling is a cutting-edge technology that is currently gaining popularity in India. In the Indian state of Maharashtra, near the city of Mumbai, is where the G+20 Residential Building is located. The study's goal is to develop an intelligent model using BIM-based software for planning, analysis, scheduling, and estimate. This programme manages the various expectations and requirements of designers and contractors while addressing project complexity.

Due to predominating lateral stresses, tall constructions have continued to rise higher and higher while encountering odd loading effects and extremely high loading values. Strength, serviceability, stability, and human comfort are the design characteristics for tall buildings. As a result, lateral loads such as wind loads and seismic forces are becoming more and more significant, and practically every designer must now consider how to provide sufficient strength and stability against lateral loads. The amount of time required for design work is greatly reduced when using software like Etabs and Revit. Revit may be used to access each member's details individually. Utilizing software increases accuracy. This uses ETABS to assess a multi-story residential construction while taking into account all external influences. This project was created in accordance with IS 456:2000 of the Indian Codes.

Using Etabs, the G+20 structure was analysed, and all of the results—including storey displacement, shear, and drift—were found to be below the maximum allowable level. As a result, the structure is secure. Using Autodesk Revit 2019, an accurate 3D digital duplicate of the structure was produced.

4) ABHAY GULERIA (2014) Among the structures that regularly undergo ETABS analysis are skyscrapers, parking garages, steel and concrete buildings, low and high rise buildings, and portal frame constructions. The structural behaviour of multi-story structures for several plan configurations, including rectangular, C, L, and I-shape, is particularly discussed. A 15-story, R.C.C.-framed skyscraper is modelled for examination using the ETABS software. After the structure has been examined, maximum shear forces, bending moments, and maximum storey displacement are computed, and they are compared for all the analysed situations.

The analysis of the multi-story structure showed that there is an inverse relationship between storey height and the storey overturning moment. Additionally, the way that L-shaped and I-shaped structures react to an overturning moment is quite similar. Floor height peaked at the sixth story, at which point the storey drift displacement started to diminish. Dynamic analysis is used to generate mode forms, from which it may be deduced that asymmetrical designs deform more than symmetrical layouts. Plans that take gaps into consideration should be asymmetrical.

5) IMAD SHAKIR ABBOOD, MOHAMMED AHMED JASIM, AND SARDASHT S (2021) High-rise structures require a high level of structural stability for both safety and design purposes, making them far more complicated than low-rise structures. Here, we give information on their safety features, structural stability, and design difficulties. Here, we are using a strong structural system to withstand lateral loads brought on by seismic and wind activity. As a result, a broad overview of the behaviour of various structural systems for various high-rise building heights is shown by the use of several nonlinear static procedure studies (pushover) and nonlinear dynamic procedure analyses (for wind and earthquake loading).

High-rise structures, including their definition, safety features, design considerations, structural stability, and linear and nonlinear analysis for static and dynamic processes brought on by wind and seismic activity. The study includes concise summaries of several structural systems that can be found in both books and the public domain. A critical evaluation of the existing simplified models as well as the seismic energy base design are also provided. Researchers need to pay more attention to serviceability issues such as floor vibration, lateral sway, and occupant comfort as high-rise buildings are created more frequently employing lighter members. For the future generation of sustainable mega-structures and extremely tall buildings, novel structural solutions must be created.

Outcomes From Literature

- Building skyscrapers is a huge undertaking, and the construction team needs technology to aid in a flawless completion of the task. BIM (Building Information Modeling) is used to reduce project costs, time, and energy use.
- A number of tools and simulation techniques are used to build a BIM model for carrying out structural engineering design, including beams, frames, trusses, slabs, foundations, and finite element analysis.
- Using BIM Revit and ETABS analysis together will produce findings for structural detail analysis that will improve the precision of structural analysis.
- Design work takes much less time when done with software like Etabs and Revit. Revit may be used to access each member's details individually. Utilizing software increases accuracy.
- The examination of the multi-storey building revealed that the inverse relationship between storey height and the storey overturning moment exists.
- The results in the form of Story displacement, Story drift, Base shear, Overturning moments, Time period were found under the maximum permissible limit.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

- Planning of skyscraper building is to be done in 2D AutoCAD and 3D Modeling in Autodesk REVIT software using BIM concept.
- Analysis of skyscraper is to be carried out using CSI ETABS Software.
- To study the parameters of skyscraper such as story displacement, story drift, base shear, overturning moments, Time period.
- To compare the results of base shear obtained by Equivalent static method and Response spectrum method.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This project seeks to demonstrate how the BIM (Building Information Modelling) and structural analysis software interface functions. The project that follows involves the 2D planning of a 40-story skyscraper using Autocad software. The following plan should be imported into Autodesk Revit Architecture to be converted into a 3D model. After that, BIM should be linked with structural analysis and design in the ETABS software, allowing for a wide range of changes to be conducted and checked to ensure the best choice and investigate real structural security. The tower has a total height of 124.2 metres. Building height is maintained at 3.0 m for the remaining floors and at 3.2 m for the top five floors.

4.1 Method Used

4.1.1 Response Spectrum Method

- The Response Spectrum Analysis (Part 1) Provisions are implemented in accordance with IS Code 1893-2016.
- In order to use the response spectrum approach, the seismic zone and soil type must be selected.
- In comparison to other methods, the Response Spectrum technique produces accurate data.
- Utilizing a response spectrum analysis methodology, seismic analysis is carried out. Data such base shear, drift, and storey displacement are computed, and the outcomes are then shown on graphs for conclusions.

Table 1: Description of Skyscraper Building

Sl. No	Parameters	Specification
1.	Type of structure	Residential building.
2.	Number of storey	G+40
3.	Size of the building	(62 x 41.56) m ²
4.	Height of ground storey upto 5 th floor	3.2m
5.	Height of typical story	3.0m
6.	Height of the building	124.2m
7.	Walls	230mm thick main walls and 114mm thick partition walls.
8.	Size of Beam	Beam 450X450 mm Beam 600 X600 mm Beam 700 X700 mm Beam 750 X750 mm
9.	Size of Column	Column 800X800 mm Column 1200X1200mm
10.	Thickness of slab	150mm
11.	Height of Parapet	1.5m
12.	Material	M60 grade concrete, grade of steel Fe-550 (Longitudinal) and Fe-415(Lateral)
13.	Loads	Dead load as per IS: 875 (Part I) –1987 Live load as per IS: 875 (Part II) –1987 Wind load as per IS: 875 (Part III) –1987
14.	Design philosophy seismic	Limit state method conforming to IS456-2000 Earthquake inputs as per IS 1893 (part 1):2016 Criteria for design of tall structures as per IS code16700-2017.

15.	Soil type :	Type -I (Hard soil)
16.	Importance factor	1.5
17.	Response reduction factor	5
18.	Building location	low intensity zone
19.	Seismic Zone factor	0.10
20.	Density of Red brick	19.2 kN/m ³

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 General

For the examination of a structure model Response Spectrum strategies are applied. The examination of the distinctive structure model is finished by utilizing ETABS programming. The investigation results, for example, story displacements, story drifts, Base Shear, Overturning moment, Time Period of a structure model are calculated and commented upon.

5.2 Storey displacement

One of the most popular methods for describing how building structures behave is the fluctuation of storey displacement along building height. In order to assess the effects, numerical simulations of the model were run in the X and Y directions. We got the response of the storey peak displacement versus storey height under linear dynamic analysis. For the response spectrum case, the built building model obtained peak displacements for each floor level as shown below.

To understand its effects, the presentation of the model using seismic burdens is focused. The displacements for the model that are most likely to occur as a result of various lateral loads are gathered and tabulated.

The maximum permitted displacement in any multi-story building is $h_s/500$, where h_s is the building's height, according to Indian regulations.

The maximum permitted displacement for the models used in the examination is equal to $124.2/500$, or 0.248 metres, or 250 millimetres.

5.3 Parameters Studied for a Model in zone II

Table 2: Maximum storey displacement of a model due to seismic load in zone II

STOREY DISPLACEMENT				
Storey Number	Load Case	X-Direction	Load Case	Y-Direction
		mm		mm
40	RSAX	12.185	RSAY	11.51
39	RSAX	12.079	RSAY	11.364
38	RSAX	11.961	RSAY	11.207

Figure 1 : Storey Displacement RS -X Direction

Figure 2: Storey Displacement RS -Y Direction

Table 3: Maximum storey displacement envelope of a model due to seismic load in zone II

ENVELOPE (STOREY DISPLACEMENT)		
Storey Number	X-Direction(mm)	Y-Direction(mm)
40	23.912	28.104
39	23.692	27.859

38	23.439	27.589
37	23.15	27.296
36	22.823	26.978
35	22.461	26.634
34	22.064	26.262
33	21.633	25.862
32	21.171	25.432
31	20.68	24.972
30	20.16	24.483
29	19.615	23.964
28	19.045	23.414
27	18.452	22.835
26	17.839	22.227
25	17.207	21.589
24	16.557	20.923
23	15.892	20.228
22	15.213	19.506
21	14.522	18.757
20	13.82	17.982
19	13.109	17.181
18	12.39	16.356
17	11.666	15.507
16	10.936	14.636
15	10.204	13.744
14	9.47	12.832
13	8.735	11.902
12	8.001	10.957
11	7.27	9.997
10	6.542	9.027
9	5.818	8.048
8	5.101	7.065
7	4.391	6.081
6	3.689	5.102
5	2.993	4.131
4	2.248	3.1
3	1.527	2.108
2	0.857	1.192
1	0.294	0.415
Base(0)	0	0

Figure 3: Max Storey Displacement RS –X,Y Direction

5.4 Storey drift

Storey drift is the lateral movement of one floor with respect to another level when normalised by floor height (i.e., above or below). Seismic analysis, a method for evaluating the structural behaviour of damaged structures, has made it possible to identify these issues. Storey drift that exceeded a standard limit caused damage to the building. Dynamic Response Spectrum is employed to evaluate the impact of the building model. The Response Spectrum analysis of the X and Y directions of the storey drift graph contained the results summarised in the table below.

According to IS 1893-2016, storey drift was examined. The most permissible drift for any structure is equal to 0.004H, where H is the height of one storey of a building.

For our model greatest permissible drift = 0.004*3.0=0.012m = 12mm

Table 4: Maximum story drifts of a model due to seismic load in zone II

STOREY DRIFT					
Storey Number	Load Case	X-Dir	Storey Number	Load Case	Y-Dir
6	RSAX	0.000141	12	RSAY	0.000123
5	RSAX	0.000144	11	RSAY	0.000124
4	RSAX	0.000143	10	RSAY	0.000123

Figure 4 : Storey Drift RS-X Direction

Figure 5 : Storey Drift RS-Y Direction

Table 5 : Maximum storey drift envelope of a model due to seismic load in zone II

ENVELOPE (STOREY DRIFT)		
Storey Number	X-Direction (mm)	Y-Direction (mm)
40	0.000073	0.000081
39	0.000084	0.00009
38	0.000096	0.000098
37	0.000109	0.000106
36	0.000121	0.000115
35	0.000132	0.000125
34	0.000143	0.000135
33	0.000154	0.000146
32	0.000164	0.000155
31	0.000173	0.000165

30	0.000182	0.000174
29	0.00019	0.000183
28	0.000197	0.000193
27	0.000204	0.000203
26	0.000211	0.000213
25	0.000216	0.000222
24	0.000222	0.000232
23	0.000226	0.000241
22	0.00023	0.00025
21	0.000234	0.000258
20	0.000237	0.000267
19	0.00024	0.000275
18	0.000242	0.000283
17	0.000243	0.00029
16	0.000244	0.000297
15	0.000245	0.000304
14	0.000245	0.00031
13	0.000245	0.000315
12	0.000244	0.00032
11	0.000243	0.000324
10	0.000241	0.000326
9	0.000239	0.000328
8	0.000237	0.000328
7	0.000234	0.000326
6	0.000232	0.000324
5	0.000233	0.000322
4	0.000225	0.00031
3	0.000209	0.000286
2	0.000176	0.000243
1	0.000092	0.00013
Base(0)	0	0

Figure 6 : Max Storey Drift RS-X, Y Direction

5.5 Storey overturning moment

Under seismic forces applied individually in X and Y direction. The building frame model is examined and related finding and tabulated below. The curves illustrated how the number of storey overturning moment varies along with building height in both X & Y direction.

Table 6: Maximum overturning of a model due to seismic load in zone II

STOREY OVERTURNING MOMENT				
Storey Number	Load Case	Y-Dir	Load Case	X-Dir
		kN-m		kN-m
2	RSAX	303220.4148	RSAY	234971.9279
1	RSAX	315526.956	RSAY	244584.352
Base(0)	RSAX	328058.3089	RSAY	254407.5038

Figure 7 : Storey Overturning Moment RS-Y Direction

Figure 8 : Storey Overturning Moment RS-X Direction

Table 7 : Maximum storey overturning moment envelope of a model due to seismic load in zone II

ENVELOPE (MAX STOREY OVERTURNING MOMENT)		
Storey Number	X-Direction(mm)	Y-Direction(mm)
40	487651.2752	-1707392
39	1074017.866	-4305074
38	1660384.457	-6902756
37	2246751.048	-9500437
36	2833117.639	-12098119
35	3419484.229	-14695801
34	4005850.82	-17293483
33	4592217.411	-19891165
32	5178584.002	-22488846
31	5764950.593	-25086528
30	6351317.184	-27684210
29	6937683.774	-30281892
28	7524050.365	-32879574
27	8110416.956	-35477255
26	8696783.547	-38074937
25	9283150.138	-40672619
24	9869516.729	-43270301
23	10455883	-45867983
22	11042250	-48465664
21	11628617	-51063346
20	12214983	-53661028
19	12801350	-56258710
18	13387716	-58856392
17	13974083	-61454073
16	14560449	-64051755
15	15146816	-66649437
14	15733183	-69247119
13	16319549	-71844801
12	16905916	-74442482
11	17492282	-77040164
10	18078649	-79637846
9	18665016	-82235528
8	19251382	-84833209
7	19837749	-87430891
6	20424115	-90028573
5	21010482	-92626255
4	21606849	-95246166
3	22203216	-97866077
2	22799583	-100485987
1	23399718	-103112875
Base(0)	69595232	-34656296

Figure 9 :Max Storey Overturning Moment RS-X,Y Direction

5.6 Storey Shear

In seismic design, shear forces measures in terms of shear at base and shear at each shear forces at each storey. The computed shear force values while accounting and disregarding the impact of building model.

EQUIVALENT STATIC METHOD

The equivalent static method of finding lateral forces is also known as the static method or the seismic coefficient method. The structure is treated as discrete system having concentrated masses at floor levels which comprise the weight of columns and walls in any Storey should be equally distributed to the floors above and below the Storey. In addition, the suitable amount of imposed load at this floor is also lumped with it. It is also assumed that the structure flexible and will deflect with respect to the position of foundation; the lumped mass system reduces to the solution of a system of second order differential equations. These equations are formed by distribution of mass and stiffness in a structure, together with its damping characteristics of the ground motion.

Table 8 :Maximum story shear of a model due to seismic load in zone II

Story	EQUIVALENT STATIC METHOD		RESPONSE SPECTRUM METHOD	
	EQX	EQY	RSAX	RSAY
	kN	kN	kN	kN
40	319.0153	242.6003	285.9776	337.9155
39	639.2176	500.9107	552.2139	639.349
38	943.3453	746.2537	784.6614	888.1387

7	1231.8124	978.9631	986.4783	1091.7981
36	1505.033	1199.3729	1160.4438	1258.2103
35	1763.4208	1407.8171	1309.5032	1394.6228
34	2007.3899	1604.6294	1437.5633	1507.7657
33	2237.3542	1790.144	1548.4047	1603.4651
32	2453.7275	1964.6946	1645.6344	1687.1102
31	2656.9239	2128.6152	1732.7968	1762.9099
30	2847.3573	2282.2398	1812.5926	1833.557
29	3025.4417	2425.9022	1887.0823	1901.0961
28	3191.5908	2559.9365	1958.1434	1966.5828
27	3346.2188	2684.6765	2026.8722	2030.1786
26	3489.7395	2800.4561	2093.6883	2092.0656
25	3622.5668	2907.6093	2159.0806	2152.1294
24	3745.1148	3006.4699	2223.3144	2210.1794
23	3857.7973	3097.3721	2286.3104	2266.5542
22	3961.0282	3180.6495	2348.2242	2321.4326
21	4055.2216	3256.6363	2409.1353	2375.0111
20	4140.7913	3325.6662	2468.7408	2427.9382
19	4218.1513	3388.0733	2527.0063	2480.4502
18	4287.7155	3444.1914	2583.9963	2532.6405
17	4349.8978	3494.3546	2639.3712	2584.8422
16	4405.1122	3538.8966	2693.156	2636.7723
15	4453.7727	3578.1515	2745.8231	2688.1678
14	4496.293	3612.4531	2797.4134	2739.2399
13	4533.0873	3642.1354	2848.2237	2789.7901
12	4564.5694	3667.5324	2899.3312	2840.2269
11	4591.1533	3688.9778	2951.4165	2891.9037
10	4613.2529	3706.8058	3005.0758	2945.6677
9	4631.2821	3721.3501	3061.6197	3002.8001
8	4645.6548	3732.9448	3121.5341	3064.9828
7	4656.7851	3741.9237	3184.5341	3132.3639
6	4665.0868	3748.6207	3250.8587	3204.796
5	4671.0226	3753.4092	3319.4013	3281.7559
4	4674.8526	3756.4989	3384.7732	3356.9451
3	4677.007	3758.2369	3445.4731	3426.4146
2	4677.9645	3759.0093	3495.4625	3483.2145
1	4678.2051	3759.2034	3519.045	3510.0354

Figure 10 : Comparison of Base Shear In X Direction

Figure 11 : Comparison of Base Shear In Y Direction

In order to guarantee the minimum strength of a structure constructed using Response Spectrum Method. Under the seismic design rules the induced base shear is practiced. The equivalent static approach is used to calibrate the seismic base shear brought on by Response Spectrum analysis. So to be on safe side scaling have been done as per the provision of IS code 1893-2016 (clause 7.7.3).

Table 9: Maximum story shear of a model due to seismic load in zone II

STOREY SHEAR						
Storey Number	Load Case	Location	X-Dir	Load Case	Location	X-Dir
			kN			kN
40	RSAX	Top	382.3521	RSAY	Top	363.935
		Bottom	382.3521		Bottom	363.935
39	RSAX	Top	738.3099	RSAY	Top	688.5789
		Bottom	738.3099		Bottom	688.5789
38	RSAX	Top	1049.0922	RSAY	Top	956.5254
		Bottom	1049.0922		Bottom	956.5254
37	RSAX	Top	1318.9214	RSAY	Top	1175.8665
		Bottom	1318.9214		Bottom	1175.8665

36	RSAX	Top	1551.5131	RSAY	Top	1355.0925
		Bottom	1551.5131		Bottom	1355.0925
35	RSAX	Top	1750.8057	RSAY	Top	1502.0088
		Bottom	1750.8057		Bottom	1502.0088
34	RSAX	Top	1922.0219	RSAY	Top	1623.8637
		Bottom	1922.0219		Bottom	1623.8637
33	RSAX	Top	2070.2169	RSAY	Top	1726.9319
		Bottom	2070.2169		Bottom	1726.9319
32	RSAX	Top	2200.213	RSAY	Top	1817.0176
		Bottom	2200.213		Bottom	1817.0176
31	RSAX	Top	2316.7491	RSAY	Top	1898.6539
		Bottom	2316.7491		Bottom	1898.6539
30	RSAX	Top	2423.4361	RSAY	Top	1974.7409
		Bottom	2423.4361		Bottom	1974.7409
29	RSAX	Top	2523.0288	RSAY	Top	2047.4805
		Bottom	2523.0288		Bottom	2047.4805
28	RSAX	Top	2618.0375	RSAY	Top	2118.0096
		Bottom	2618.0375		Bottom	2118.0096
27	RSAX	Top	2709.9278	RSAY	Top	2186.5023
		Bottom	2709.9278		Bottom	2186.5023
26	RSAX	Top	2799.261	RSAY	Top	2253.1547
		Bottom	2799.261		Bottom	2253.1547
25	RSAX	Top	2886.6905	RSAY	Top	2317.8433
		Bottom	2886.6905		Bottom	2317.8433
24	RSAX	Top	2972.5711	RSAY	Top	2380.3632
		Bottom	2972.5711		Bottom	2380.3632
23	RSAX	Top	3056.7967	RSAY	Top	2441.0788
		Bottom	3056.7967		Bottom	2441.0788
22	RSAX	Top	3139.5754	RSAY	Top	2500.1828
		Bottom	3139.5754		Bottom	2500.1828
21	RSAX	Top	3221.0136	RSAY	Top	2557.8868
		Bottom	3221.0136		Bottom	2557.8868
20	RSAX	Top	3300.7061	RSAY	Top	2614.8894
		Bottom	3300.7061		Bottom	2614.8894
19	RSAX	Top	3378.6071	RSAY	Top	2671.4448
		Bottom	3378.6071		Bottom	2671.4448
18	RSAX	Top	3454.8028	RSAY	Top	2727.6538
		Bottom	3454.8028		Bottom	2727.6538
17	RSAX	Top	3528.8389	RSAY	Top	2783.875
		Bottom	3528.8389		Bottom	2783.875
16	RSAX	Top	3600.7493	RSAY	Top	2839.8037
		Bottom	3600.7493		Bottom	2839.8037
15	RSAX	Top	3671.1651	RSAY	Top	2895.1567
		Bottom	3671.1651		Bottom	2895.1567
14	RSAX	Top	3740.1414	RSAY	Top	2950.1614

		Bottom	3740.1414		Bottom	2950.1614
13	RSAX	Top	3808.0747	RSAY	Top	3004.6039
		Bottom	3808.0747		Bottom	3004.6039
12	RSAX	Top	3876.4055	RSAY	Top	3058.9243
		Bottom	3876.4055		Bottom	3058.9243
11	RSAX	Top	3946.0434	RSAY	Top	3114.5803
		Bottom	3946.0434		Bottom	3114.5803
10	RSAX	Top	4017.786	RSAY	Top	3172.484
		Bottom	4017.786		Bottom	3172.484
9	RSAX	Top	4093.3851	RSAY	Top	3234.0157
		Bottom	4093.3851		Bottom	3234.0157
8	RSAX	Top	4173.4907	RSAY	Top	3300.9864
		Bottom	4173.4907		Bottom	3300.9864
7	RSAX	Top	4257.7216	RSAY	Top	3373.5558
		Bottom	4257.7216		Bottom	3373.5558
6	RSAX	Top	4346.3977	RSAY	Top	3451.5652
		Bottom	4346.3977		Bottom	3451.5652
5	RSAX	Top	4438.0391	RSAY	Top	3534.4511
		Bottom	4438.0391		Bottom	3534.4511
4	RSAX	Top	4525.4413	RSAY	Top	3615.4298
		Bottom	4525.4413		Bottom	3615.4298
3	RSAX	Top	4606.5971	RSAY	Top	3690.2485
		Bottom	4606.5971		Bottom	3690.2485
2	RSAX	Top	4673.4328	RSAY	Top	3751.4219
		Bottom	4673.4328		Bottom	3751.4219
1	RSAX	Top	4704.9628	RSAY	Top	3780.3081
		Bottom	4704.9628		Bottom	3780.3081

STOREY SHEAR IN RS -X DIRECTION

Figure 12 : Storey Shear In RS- X Direction

STOREY SHEAR IN RS –Y DIRECTION

Figure 13 : Storey Shear In RS- Y Direction

Figure 14 : Comparison Of Base Shear In RSAX And RSAY Direction

5.7 Fundamental Natural Period

The basic natural period, one of a structure's most dynamic features, is the amount of time required to complete one oscillation cycle.

As per code time period(T_a)= $0.075h^{0.75} = 0.075 * 124.2^{0.75} = 3.79 \text{ sec} \sim 4 \text{ seconds}$

The time period for the building model that were taken into consideration and tabulated below:

Table 10 : Maximum Time Period of a model due to seismic load in zone II

MAX TIME PERIOD	
Mode	Period (in sec)
1	3.11
2	2.77
3	2.503

5.8 Maximum Time Period Of A Model

Figure 15 : Maximum Time Period (In Bar Graph)

Figure 16: Maximum Time Period

VI. OBSERVATIONS

1. It was noted that BIM (Building Information Modeling) saved time, energy, and project costs, reduced the need for comprehensive checks, and helped to minimize documentation errors that could have a negative impact on construction.
2. When ETABS analysis is integrated with BIM (AutoCAD and Revit), thorough structural analysis results are produced, which will improve the precision of structural analysis.
3. Maximum storey displacement occurred is 23.912mm in X-direction and 28.104mm in Y direction which is less than permissible limit 250mm. Hence the skyscraper is safe.
4. a) Storey drift increased with storey height upto 5th floor reaching maximum value i.e., 0.000144 and then start to decreases continously in X-direction.
 b) In Y-direction, storey drift increased with storey height upto 11th floor floor reaching maximum value i.e.,0.000124 and start to decrease continuously upto top level.
5. The conclusion is documented in the literature(8) i.e.,the stórey òverturning mòment is inversely proportional with storey height.

6. In the X and Y directions, respectively, base shear for ESM is found to be 32.93% and 7.1% higher than for RSM.
7. As per the results obtained for base shear, Response Spectrum method are multiplied by multiplying factor 1.329 in X direction and for Y direction multiplied by multiplying factor by 1.071 as per codal provision IS 1893-2016(part 1).
8. The results in the form of Story displacement, Story drift, Base shear, Overturning moments, Time period were found under the maximum permissible limit.

VII. CONCLUSION

The following findings were drawn from the study mentioned above:

1. BIM in structural engineering reduced the number of request for information items from contractors and makes possible the visualization design.
2. Maximum storey displacement occurred is 23.912mm in X-direction and 28.104mm in Y direction which is less than permissible limit 250mm. Hence the skyscraper is safe.
3. Maximum Storey drift ratio in X direction is 0.000245 and in Y direction is 0.000328 which is less than permissible value 0.012 .
4. The conclusion is documented in the literature(8) i.e.,the storey overturning moment is inversely proportional with storey height.
5. It is found that ESM gives 32.93% more base shear value as compared to RSM in X direction and 7.1% in Y direction, so to be on safe side base shear scaling is done i.e., multiplying factor with 1.329 in X direction and for Y direction multiplying factor with 1.071 as per codal provision 1893-2016 to ensured that minimum strength of designed structure using RSM is similar to strength of designed structure using ESM.
6. For safe skyscraper, maximum time period of first three modes are 3.11,2.77,2.503 seconds which is less than 4 seconds as per codal provision IS 1893-2016 (part 1).

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